

THE ALGEBRA IN NATURAL STRUCTURES

FRANCESCO PEÑA-GARCIA AND JOHN MEDINA-DIAZ

ABSTRACT. Natural structures are assembled with the formation of NE-connections which are a generalization of attraction forces. Here, we construct two nested axiomatic systems in which NE-connections can be understood as an algebraic operation. Then, we define a partial order \leq that represents the relation “being part of” between the elements of the space of natural entities. We prove that the collection of elements of an arbitrary natural structure n which is denoted as X_n is a commutative semigroup (X_n, \bullet) in which every element is idempotent. The operator \bullet represents the act of NE-connecting. We follow this by proving the codefinition of \leq and \bullet in finite NEs as well as their compatibility. Finally, we propose a mathematical definition of the collection of families of NE-connections and point out its relationship with X_n .

1. INTRODUCTION

The theory of Natural Structures emerged at the beginning of this century [2] as a unifying framework of science. This work is a step forward in the development of this theory through the axiomatization of some of its algebraic properties. The fundamental object of the theory of natural structures is a *natural structure*, abbreviated as NE. This object is a distributed whole produced by natural processes. Being a “whole” means that every element of the NE is connected with every other element. These “connections” are called “NE-connections” which are “bonds” between entities in the most general sense. Hence, the wholeness of NEs arise from the underlying NE-connections. We can take the act of NE-connecting, i.e., the formation of NEs, as a law of composition inside NEs.

Some examples are in order. First, consider an atom such as helium. It is formed by two electrons, two protons, and two neutrons. All of them are a whole and thus any part of it is also a whole. For instance, the electron cloud. Since negative repels negative, the electrons are not NE-connected by forces between them but by an indirect NE-connection which is the bond between electrons and protons. Another example is a pack of wolves. There is no physical bond between them that keeps them together, in this case the NE-connection is in the mind of the wolfs.

The intuition behind this law of composition is later formalized with an axiomatization of the fundamental ideas of theory of natural structures that are involved in this process. The theory that emerges from this axiomatization will be called η -theory. This is the theory of the fundamentals of the algebra of NE-connections. From this it

2020 *Mathematics Subject Classification*. Primary 20M14, 08A02, 06A06.

Key words and phrases. Algebraic Structure, Order theory, Natural Structure.

will be natural to realize how some basic properties of NE-connections such as reflexivity, commutativity, and idempotence arise from the basic notions that are captured in the axioms of η -theory. The aim of this paper is to complete this formalization and go further by analyzing more complex algebraic properties of NE-connections inside NEs.

η -theory is based on set theory but it is not *just* set theory. In η -theory, each entity e can be identified with a unique set X_e . However, we need an apparatus that tells us how to relate these sets in a meaningful way to understand NE-connections, this is η -theory. η -theory is based on 9 axioms grouped in 2 axiomatic systems (see appendix A). The first system of 7 axioms is called $\eta - E$ *axiomatic system*, it describes the function-behavior of η that assigns a natural entity to every non-empty set of natural entities. It also partially defines the space of natural entities, which is denoted as E , and the structure of entities. The second system of 2 axioms is called $\eta - SNE$ *axiomatic system*. It describes the behaviour of natural structures and their constituents.

In the following we introduce the most important theorems of this paper. They will be presented rather informally to avoid the mention of symbols and concepts that will be timely defined and formalized in the sequel.

Natural entities will be then understood as elements in an abstract space called the *space of natural entities* that will be denoted by E . This space is taken as a primitive, i.e., something that we claim to exist and on which we will base our discussion. The structure of E will simply be the one of a class in the sense of NBG set theory. Inside E , we define a relation called “being part of” that is represented by the symbol \leq . The notion of equality in E is formally defined as $a = b \iff a \leq b \wedge b \leq a$.

Theorem 1. *The relation \leq is a partial order in E .*

Following this, we study the structure of each element of E . We denote the collection of elements of $e \in E$ as X_e . With the aid of the order relation this can be readily defined as $X_e := \{n \in E : n \leq e\}$. Many of the subsequent propositions benefit from the fact that (X_e, \leq) is a poset. Whenever $n \in E$ is an NE, X_n will acquire more properties that are based on the NE-connections. To understand this, we need to define another function that associates each pair of NE-connected entities with the NE that is produced upon this NE-connection. This function is denoted by \bullet .

Theorem 2. *The function \bullet is surjective in the subspace of natural structures.*

This means that \bullet is playing a key role in the formation of NEs. The following is the central theorem of this paper.

Theorem 3. *(X_n, \bullet) is a commutative semigroup in which every element is idempotent.*

Therefore, every NE can be associated with an algebraic structure. This allows us to use a wealth of mathematical techniques developed for semigroups in the study of NEs. The next result is a technical theorem. It provides another link between \bullet and η inside NEs.

Theorem 4. *For every finite and non-empty subset $I \subset X_n$, the projection of $\{I\}$ on the space of natural entities is the NE that is the successive operation with \bullet of the elements of I .*

The next theorem can be interpreted as the codefinition of \leq and \bullet inside finite NEs.

Theorem 5. *For every finite NE n , $(\forall x_i, x_j \in X_n)(x_i \leq x_j \iff x_i \bullet x_j = x_j)$.*

This renders the following theorem most apparent.

Theorem 6. *In every finite X_n , collection of elements of a finite NE, \leq is compatible with \bullet in the sense that*

$$(\forall a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 \in X_n)(a_1 \leq b_1 \wedge a_2 \leq b_2 \implies a_1 \bullet a_2 \leq b_1 \bullet b_2)$$

The structure of the paper is divided as follows. In section 2 we provide some clarifying remarks on the notation that will be used on the paper. In section 3 we introduce part of the $\eta - E$ axiomatic system. In section 4 we give the structure of a poset to the space of natural entities and provide the last axiom of the $\eta - E$ axiomatic system. In section 5 we present the $\eta - SNE$ axiomatic system. We also define the function \bullet and show some of its properties. In section 6 we prove that (X_n, \bullet) is a commutative semigroup and introduce the \prod notation. In section 7 we study how order and algebra are related in finite NEs. In section 8 we connect our results for X_n with C_n , the second of the three components of NEs. Finally, in section 9 future developments of this theory are proposed as well as a short discussion on D_n , the third and last component of NEs.

2. NOTATION REMARKS

Before moving to the main body of this paper, some notation remarks are in order. Using NE notation [1], we define (X_n, D_n, C_n) as the representation of the NE n . Here, X_n is the collection of all of the elements of n , D_n is the distribution of elements of X_n , and C_n is a family of collections of NE-connections among the elements. For an arbitrary NE, we simply write (X, D, C) as its representation with no indexing.

Regarding the statement of well-formed formulas, to a large extent, we follow the convention of writing *(quantifiers)(properties)* when referred to first-order logic. Further, although not grammatically right, we write commas between quantifiers to clarify the reading. Finally, the symbol “ \subset ” will be interpreted as “subset of” and should not be interpreted as “proper subset of”.

Finally, whenever the context is clear enough we simply write “entities” in place of “natural entities”.

3. FORMALIZATION OF “MATHEMATICAL REPRESENTATIONS”

In this section we will state and justify the first six axioms of the $\eta - E$ axiomatic system. After that we will leave the intuitive and informal talk and base our work on the axiomatic systems that will be proposed here and in the following section.

First, we recall the definition of natural structure in [2], a natural structure (NE) is a distribution of elements which are NE-connected at least in pairs. The elements and the NE-connections together constitute a whole which is formed by natural processes. Here, a connection is anything that will not permit two or more entities to be separated under standard conditions.

Since our goal is to study the mathematical properties of NEs, it is unavoidable to work with mathematical models of the objects we wish to study. For NEs, the canonical model is (X, D, C) [1]. However, for natural entities that are not NEs, there is no candidate for a canonical representation. Instead of proposing a canonical model for natural entities, we regard them as “points”, basic elements, or primitives. We wish for these primitives, however, to retain their fundamental properties of the natural world even though we cannot explicitly represent them. We formalize this approach together with our understanding of mathematical representations (models) with the $\eta - E$ axiomatic system that will be introduced in this section and the following.

For any mathematical or natural entity ν , let $P(\nu)$ be the class of its properties. If ν is a mathematical entity, among the elements of $P(\nu)$ there is a trivial property that states that ν is a mathematical object, let, $P^+(\nu)$ will be the set of non-trivial properties of ν in the above sense.

For any V , collection of mathematical objects, and set G^+ defined as $G^+ := G \cup \{\emptyset\}$ where G is any subset of E , we can define the following relation $H \subset V \times G^+$ as

$$(1) \quad \nu H g \iff P^+(\nu) \subset P(g) \vee g = \emptyset$$

in other words, every element of V is related to $\emptyset \in G^+$ by H while some elements of V may be related to elements of $G \subset E$. It is also possible that for any $\nu \in V$ and any $g \in G$ $\nu H g$ is not true. Bear in mind that the properties in any $P(x)$ can be expressed in different ways. We will denote by the same symbol H all of the relations that are defined on the different combinations of collections of mathematical objects and subsets of E appended with \emptyset . Since these relations are defined with the same property (eq. (1)) there will be no confusion.

For a fixed V , we want to relate V with the biggest set or class G^+ in the sense of inclusion such that every element of G is related by H to at least one element of V .

Definition 3.1. For a given V , collection of mathematical objects, $\eta(V)$ is a subset of E such that

- (1) $(\forall g \in \eta(V), \exists \nu \in V)(\nu H g)$.
- (2) If G' holds 1., i.e., $(\forall g \in G', \exists \nu \in V)(\nu H g)$, then $G' \subset \eta(V)$.

If $\eta(V)$ exists and it is non-empty, $\eta(V)$ is called the projection of V on E . Observe that in 1. H is defined in $V \times (\eta(V) \cup \{\emptyset\})$ whereas in 2., H is defined on $V \times (G' \cup \{\emptyset\})$.

If V has a projection, then the elements of V will be mathematical models of the entities in $\eta(V) \subset E$. If V has no projection, we write $\eta(V) = \emptyset$. We need to remark that if the projection of V exists, it is unique. This follows immediately from the second property of definition 3.1.

It is important to remark that definition 3.1 does not put restrictions on V . Indeed, there may be elements of V that are not related to any element of $\eta(V)$, these elements have no projection on E . Two different collections of mathematical objects V and V' may have the same projection $\eta(V) = \eta(V')$. Let ν be a mathematical object, $\eta(\{\nu\})$ may be empty or contain one or many elements. Intuitively, the simpler ν is, the more elements that will be in $\eta(\{\nu\})$.

A natural question is whether we can partition E in subsets $\eta(\{\nu\})$ for ν in some special collection V^E . In other words, is there a family $\{\eta(\{\nu\})\}_{\nu \in V^E}$ such that

$$\bigcup_{\nu \in V^E} \eta(\{\nu\}) = E$$

with every $\eta(\{\nu\}) \neq \emptyset$ and $\nu \neq \nu' \implies \eta(\{\nu\}) \cap \eta(\{\nu'\}) = \emptyset$? The following axiom asserts that this is trivially possible.

Axiom 3.2. *Let $V^E := \{\{\{e\}\} : e \in E\}$, for every $\{\{e\}\} \in V^E$,*

$$\eta(\{\{e\}\}) = \{e\}$$

It is straightforward that $\{\eta(\{\{e\}\})\}_{\{e\} \in V^E}$ is a partition of E . This overwhelming notation will be justified in the following. First, we need to comment on the philosophical justification of axiom 3.2. When we construct the space of natural entities E , every natural entity is “modeled” by a point-like element of E . We call them points because we have no access to their mathematical structure; however, we also know that this modelling is perfect in the sense that all the properties of the natural elements *are* in the elements of E . To reconcile these apparently contradictory facts, axiom 3.2 asserts that the only element of E that includes all the properties of e is e itself. That being said, another mathematical object ν could be a model of e , thus implying $e \in \eta(\{\nu\})$.

Notice that in axiom 3.2 we write $\eta(\{\{e\}\})$ instead of $\eta(\{e\})$ because $V = \{\{e\}\}$ must be a collection of mathematical objects, in this case $\{e\}$. If we set $V = \{e\}$, that would mean that e is a mathematical object which is not inherently wrong but then working with $V = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ would be of little use since we would not be able to uphold the following axiom.

Axiom 3.3. *For every $Y \subset E$ non-empty, there exists a unique entity $\hat{e} \in E$ such that*

$$\eta(\{Y\}) = \{\hat{e}\}$$

If, instead of $\eta(\{Y\})$, we state axiom 3.3 in terms of $\eta(Y)$, it would not be fundamental in the following sense. Take for instance $Y = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\} \subset E$. Recall from definition 3.1 that the projection of Y on E is the biggest subset of E such that

$$(\forall g \in \eta(\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}), \exists e_i \in \{e_1, \dots, e_n\})(e_i H g)$$

Since we can agree on that $e_i H e_i$ for all $e_i \in Y$, then $Y \subset \eta(Y)$. Therefore, $\eta(Y) = \{\hat{e}\}$ would make little sense unless Y is a singleton. On the other hand, $\eta(\{\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}\})$ is the biggest subset of E such that

$$(\forall g \in \eta(\{\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}\}))(\{e_1, \dots, e_n\} H g)$$

Axiom 3.3 states that this element g exists and it is unique.

Observe that axiom 3.3 does not imply axiom 3.2 since it would only assert that $\eta(\{\{e\}\}) = \{\hat{e}\}$ with the possibility that $e \neq \hat{e}$. Axiom 3.3 says that every collection of entities is represented uniquely by another entity which could be of a different type. For instance, an arbitrary collection of NEs need not to be an NE. Likewise, a collection of solid objects could be a gas.

If $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{\hat{e}\}$, we say that the elements of Y are part of \hat{e} , this idea will be further developed in the next section. Since $\eta(\{\{e\}\}) = \{e\}$ this implies that e is a part of itself which is a slight abuse of language.

Going back to our previous terminology, we say that Y is a model or mathematical representation of \hat{e} whenever $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{\hat{e}\}$. This does not mean that it is necessarily the unique mathematical representation of \hat{e} that is also a subset of E , in fact, axiom 3.2 tells us that $Y' = \{\hat{e}\}$ is also another model of \hat{e} given that $Y \neq Y'$, i.e., $\eta(\{Y'\}) = \{\hat{e}\}$. The following axioms will clarify this “multi-representativity”. But first, let us agree on the following.

Axiom 3.4. $\eta(\{\emptyset\}) = \emptyset$.

Accepting that there could be an element in $\eta(\{\emptyset\})$ leads to philosophical problems and presents no direct usefulness for the algebra that we aim to develop. Returning to the problem of multi-representativity, our answer and solution is the next axiom.

Axiom 3.5. For every non-empty family $\{Y_i\}_{i \in I}$ of non-empty subsets of E , such that $(\forall i, j \in I)(\eta(\{Y_i\}) = \eta(\{Y_j\}))$ it follows that for every $j \in I$, $\eta(\{\bigcup_{i \in I} Y_i\}) = \eta(\{Y_j\})$.

If we set $\eta(\{Y_i\}) = \{e\}$ for some $i \in I$, then every Y_j in axiom 3.5 is a model of e . Continuing with the idea that the elements of Y are parts of e whenever $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{e\}$, the following axiom clarifies the relation between subcollections of Y and e .

Axiom 3.6. $(\forall I \subset E, \forall J \subset I)(\eta(\{I\}) = \{n\} \wedge \eta(\{J\}) = \{m\} \implies \eta(\{\{m\} \cup I \setminus J\}) = \{n\})$

It is implicit that $I \neq \emptyset$ because if $I = \emptyset$, then by axiom 3.4, $\eta(\{I\}) = \emptyset$, then such I does not satisfies the condition $\eta(\{I\}) = \{n\}$. Similar to the setting of axiom 3.5, I and $\{m\} \cup I \setminus J$ are models of the entity n , this motivates us to propose the following definition.

Definition 3.7. In $\wp(E) \setminus \{\emptyset\}$, we define the following relation for $I_1, I_2 \in \wp(E) \setminus \{\emptyset\}$,

$$I_1 \cong I_2 \iff \eta(\{I_1\}) = \eta(\{I_2\})$$

Proposition 3.8. \cong is an equivalence relation in $\wp(E) \setminus \{\emptyset\}$.

Proof. It is routine work to check that \cong is reflexive, symmetric and transitive. First, for all $I_1 \subset E$, non-empty, $\eta(\{I_1\}) = \eta(\{I_1\})$, then $I_1 \cong I_1$. Second, if $I_1 \cong I_2$, then $\eta(\{I_1\}) = \eta(\{I_2\})$, i.e., $\eta(\{I_2\}) = \eta(\{I_1\})$, then $I_2 \cong I_1$. Lastly, if $I_1 \cong I_2$ and $I_2 \cong I_3$, then $\eta(\{I_1\}) = \eta(\{I_3\})$, i.e., $I_1 \cong I_3$. \square

A sort of converse of axiom 3.6 is natural to accept.

Axiom 3.9. $(\forall I, J \subset E)(\eta(\{J\}) = \{m\} \wedge \eta(\{I \cup \{m\}\}) = \{n\} \implies \eta(\{I \cup J\}) = \{n\})$

Once again, the subset J in axiom 3.9 that interest us is non-empty, otherwise $\eta(\{J\}) = \{m\}$ would be false. I could be empty and there would not be a contradiction, indeed $\eta(\{I \cup \{m\}\}) = \{n\}$ would imply that $\eta(\{\{m\}\}) = \{n\}$, axiom 3.2 requires that $n = m$, therefore $\eta(\{I \cup J\}) = \eta(\{J\}) = \{m\} = \{n\}$.

Proposition 3.10. $(\forall I \subset E, \forall J \subset I)(\eta(\{J\}) = \{m\} \wedge \eta(\{\{m\} \cup I \setminus J\}) = \{n\} \implies \eta(\{I\}) = \{n\})$

Proof. Let $I \setminus J = I_1$, then axiom 3.9 implies that $\eta(\{I_1 \cup J\}) = \eta(\{I\}) = \{n\}$. \square

With the six proposed axioms, we impose some kind of *set-behaviour* to every entity in E . These six axioms define η and also partially define E . We can summarize them with the following theorem.

Theorem 3.11. *There exists a function ∂ from $\wp(E)$ to $\hat{E} \cup \{\emptyset\}$ with $\hat{E} := \{\{e\} : e \in E\}$ such that*

- (1) $(\forall s \in \wp(E))(\partial(s) = s \iff |s| = 1 \vee s = \emptyset)$.
- (2) *Let $I \neq \emptyset$, then for any family $\{s_i\}_{i \in I} \subset \wp(E)$ such that $(\forall i, j \in I)(\partial(s_i) = \partial(s_j))$, then $\partial(\cup_{i \in I} s_i) = \partial(s_j)$ for any $j \in I$.*
- (3) $(\forall s \in \wp(E), \forall t \in \wp(s))(\partial((s \setminus t) \cup \partial(t)) = \partial(s))$.
- (4) $(\forall s_1, s_2 \in \wp(E))(\partial(s_1 \cup s_2) = \partial(s_1 \cup \partial(s_2)))$.

Proof. We will define ∂ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \partial : \wp(E) &\rightarrow \hat{E} \cup \{\emptyset\} \\ s &\mapsto \partial(s) = \eta(\{s\}) \end{aligned}$$

This function is well-defined since $\eta(\{s\})$ is a well-defined set by axioms 3.3 and 3.4. We will show that ∂ holds each of the four properties. For the first property, suppose $\partial(s) = s$. If s is non-empty, then axiom 3.3 implies that $\partial(s)$ is a singleton. If s has more than one element, $\partial(s) = s$ is contradictory, then s has 1 or 0 elements. To prove the converse, suppose s is a singleton, then axiom 3.2 implies that $\partial(s) = s$. If $s = \emptyset$, then axiom 3.4 implies that $\partial(s) = \emptyset = s$.

For the second property, suppose some s_i in the family $\{s_i\}_{i \in I}$ is empty, then fixing this index, for any $j \in I$, $\partial(s_j) = \partial(s_i) = \emptyset$. If there is some $\hat{j} \in I$ such that $s_{\hat{j}} \neq \emptyset$, then $\partial(s_{\hat{j}})$ would be a singleton, a contradiction. Thus every element of the family is empty, then $\partial(\cup_{i \in I} s_i) = \partial(\emptyset) = \emptyset = \partial(s_j)$ for any $j \in I$. On the other hand, if every element of the non-empty family $\{s_i\}_{i \in I}$ is non-empty, then we can directly apply axiom 3.5.

For the third property, if $s = \emptyset$, then $t = \emptyset$, thus $\partial((s \setminus t) \cup \partial(t)) = \partial(\emptyset) = \partial(s)$. If $s \neq \emptyset$, then suppose $t \neq \emptyset$, then the property follows from axiom 3.6. If $s \neq \emptyset$ and $t = \emptyset$, $\partial((s \setminus t) \cup \partial(t)) = \partial(s \cup \emptyset) = \partial(s)$.

For the last property, suppose $s_2 = \emptyset$, then $\partial(s_2) = \emptyset$, thus $\partial(s_1 \cup s_2) = \partial(s_1) = \partial(s_1 \cup \partial(s_2))$. This is true regardless s_1 is empty or not. Suppose s_2 is non-empty, then the property follows from axiom 3.9. \square

Observe that if $s \neq \emptyset$, then $\partial(s) = \eta(\{s\})$ is a singleton, thus by the property 1. of theorem 3.11, $\partial(\partial(s)) = \partial(s)$. Thus $\partial = \eta(\{\})$ is idempotent on singletons of the domain.

In next section, we show how every entity can be identified with a subset of E and also propose the last axiom of the $\eta - E$ axiomatic system.

4. E AS A PARTIALLY ORDERED SPACE

As was previously mentioned, the elements of Y can be regarded as the parts of e whenever $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{e\}$. In this section we will formalize this observation and provide E with the structure of a partially ordered space.

Definition 4.1. An entity $e_1 \in E$ is said to be a part or element of $e_2 \in E$, which we denote by $e_1 \leq e_2$, if and only if e_1 is an element of a subset Y of E such that $e_2 \in \eta(\{Y\})$. In symbols, we write

$$(2) \quad e_1 \leq e_2 \iff (\exists Y \subset E)(e_1 \in Y \wedge e_2 \in \eta(\{Y\}))$$

“ $e_1 \leq e_2$ ” can be read as “ e_1 is an element of e_2 ”, “ e_1 is a part of e_2 ”, or “ e_2 contains e_1 ”. It is obvious that Y in equation (2) cannot be empty otherwise $e_1 \in Y$ would be false. We formalize the notion of equality in E as follows.

Definition 4.2. Let $a, b \in E$, we say that $a = b$ if and only if $a \leq b \wedge b \leq a$.

In other words, two natural entities are equal if and only if one is an element of the other and vice versa.

Theorem 4.3. *The relation \leq in E is a partial order, i.e.,*

- (1) $(\forall e \in E)(e \leq e)$,
- (2) $(\forall e_1, e_2 \in E)(e_1 \leq e_2 \wedge e_2 \leq e_1 \implies e_1 = e_2)$,
- (3) $(\forall e_1, e_2, e_3 \in E)(e_1 \leq e_2 \wedge e_2 \leq e_3 \implies e_1 \leq e_3)$.

Proof. For the first condition, let $Y = \{e\}$, then $e \in Y$ and by axiom 3.2 $e \in \eta(\{Y\})$. The second condition follows directly from the definition 4.2. For the third condition, suppose $e_1 \leq e_2$ and $e_2 \leq e_3$, then there exist subsets $Y_1, Y_2 \subset E$ such that

$$e_1 \in Y_1 \wedge \eta(\{Y_1\}) = \{e_2\}$$

and

$$e_2 \in Y_2 \wedge \eta(\{Y_2\}) = \{e_3\}$$

then since $e_2 \in Y_2$, we can write $Y_2 = (Y_2 \setminus \{e_2\}) \cup \{e_2\}$, let $I = Y_2 \setminus \{e_2\}$, then

$$\eta(\{Y_2\}) = \eta(\{I \cup \{e_2\}\}) = \{e_3\}$$

Then by axiom 3.9, $\eta(\{I \cup Y_1\}) = \{e_3\}$. Since $e_1 \in Y_1 \subset I \cup Y_1$, it follows that $e_1 \leq e_3$. \square

For every $e \in E$, we denote and define the collection of all of the elements of e as

$$X_e := \{p \in E : p \leq e\}.$$

It is trivial to show that $e \in X_e$ for every $e \in E$. In section 2, it was stated that in the canonical representation (X_n, D_n, C_n) of an NE n , X_n is the collection of all the elements of the NE. Then, we can simply formalize it as

$$X_n := \{e \in E : e \leq n\}$$

as a particular case of the stated above.

Lemma 4.4. $(\forall e \in E)(\eta(\{X_e\}) = \{e\})$.

Proof. For every $p \in X_e$, $p \leq e$, then there exists $Y_p \subset E$ such that

$$p \in Y_p \wedge \eta(\{Y_p\}) = \{e\}$$

With this in mind, we construct the indexed family $\{Y_p\}_{p \in X_e}$. Since X_e is not empty, there exists at least one $p \in X_e$, thus the indexed family is non-empty and since $p \in Y_p$ for every $p \in X_e$, then the elements of the indexed family are non-empty. Then we apply axiom 3.5,

$$(3) \quad \eta\left(\bigcup_{p \in X_e} Y_p\right) = \{e\}$$

On one hand, since $\forall p \in X_e$, $p \in Y_p$, then $X_e = \bigcup_{p \in X_e} \{p\} \subset \bigcup_{p \in X_e} Y_p$. On the other hand, for every Y_p , $(\forall y \in Y_p)(y \leq e)$, then $y \in X_e$. Therefore, $Y_p \subset X_e$ implying that $\bigcup_{p \in X_e} Y_p \subset X_e$. With both inclusions, we conclude that $X_e = \bigcup_{p \in X_e} Y_p$, replacing this in equation (3), $\eta(\{X_e\}) = \{e\}$. \square

In definition 3.7, among the equivalence classes that are formed by \cong , X_e can be regarded as the canonical class representative. Indeed, if $Y \in [X_e]$, then $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{e\}$ is an intuitive and natural association.

Proposition 4.5. $(\forall e \in E, \forall M \subset X_e)(\eta(\{M\}) = \{\hat{e}\} \implies \hat{e} \leq e)$.

Proof. It is clear that M must be non-empty otherwise $\eta(\{M\}) = \emptyset$. Since $M \subset X_e$ and $\eta(\{M\}) = \{\hat{e}\}$, then axiom 3.6 implies that $\eta(\{\{\hat{e}\} \cup X_e \setminus M\}) = \{e\}$. Thus, there exists a set $Y = \{\hat{e}\} \cup X_e \setminus M \subset E$ such that $\hat{e} \in Y$ and $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{e\}$, therefore $\hat{e} \leq e$. \square

Proposition 4.6. $(\forall e \in E, \forall M \subset X_e)(\eta(\{M \cup \{e\}\}) = \{e\})$.

Proof. Since $e \in Y = M \cup \{e\}$, then its projection on E will be non-empty, let $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{\hat{e}\}$, then by definition 4.1, $e \leq \hat{e}$. On the other hand, since $M \subset X_e$ and $\{e\} \subset X_e$, $Y \subset X_e$. Therefore proposition 4.5 implies that $\hat{e} \leq e$, therefore $\hat{e} = e$. \square

Proposition 4.7. For every $a, b \in E$, if $a \leq b$, then $X_a \subset X_b$.

Proof. For every $y \in X_a$, $y \leq a$ and since $a \leq b$, then by transitivity $y \leq b$ which is the defining condition of X_b . \square

If we accept that entities are fully determined by their proper constituents, i.e., by the elements of X_e that are not e itself, then we can agree on the following axiom which is the last axiom of the $\eta - E$ axiomatic system.

Axiom 4.8. For every $a, b \in E$, if $X_a = X_b \cup \{a\}$, then $a = b$.

This says something interesting about the Hasse diagram of (X_a, \leq) . Indeed, suppose you have the following hypothetical Hasse diagram of X_a of some entity $a \in E$.

FIGURE 1. Hypothetical Hasse diagram of the collection of elements of some NE a .

Here, $X_a = \{s_1, s_2, b, a\}$ and $X_b = \{s_1, s_2, b\}$, i.e., $X_a = X_b \cup \{a\}$. Therefore, by axiom 4.8, $a = b$. Then the Hasse diagram of a collapses into

FIGURE 2. Correction of the Hasse diagram of the NE in Fig. 4.

Axiom 4.8 implies that if some element a of a hypothetical Hasse diagram is *only* connected downwards with a line to one entity b , then $a = b$ and the edge collapses. We can say that this type of “isolated” lines do not exist in Hasse diagrams of natural entities. We formalize this observation in the following proposition.

Proposition 4.9. *Let $e \in E$. If $a, b \in X_e$ such that $b \leq a$ and for all $c \in X_e$, $c \leq a \wedge a \neq c \implies c \leq b$, then $a = b$.*

Proof. Since $b \leq a$, $X_b \subset X_a$ by proposition 4.7. Then we can write

$$X_a = X_b \cup \{a\} \cup (X_a \setminus X_b)$$

Let $y \in X_a \setminus X_b$, then $y \leq a \wedge y \not\leq b$. Since $y \leq a$, if $y \neq a$ then by hypothesis $y \leq b$ which is a contradiction. It follows that $y = a$. Then $X_a \setminus X_b \subset \{a\}$. This implies that $\{a\} \cup (X_a \setminus X_b) = \{a\}$, i.e.,

$$X_a = X_b \cup \{a\}$$

Then by axiom 4.8, $a = b$. □

How is this proposition related with what we wanted to show about Hasse diagrams? First, the hypotheses $b \leq a$ and $(\forall c \in X_e)(c \leq a \wedge a \neq c \implies c \leq b)$ imply that $(\forall c \in X_e)(b \leq c \leq a \implies c = b \vee c = a)$. Assume it does not, i.e., that $(\exists c \in X_e)(b \leq c \leq a \wedge c \neq b \wedge c \neq a)$. Since $c \leq a$ and $c \neq a$, then $c \leq b$, but also $b \leq c$, then $b = c$, a contradiction. This implies that there is an edge in the Hasse diagram that connects a and b given that they are different. Second, for every edge that connects to a from below, there exists $z \in X_e$ such that $z \leq a$ and $z \neq a$, but this implies that $z \leq b$. So if we assume for a moment that $b \neq a$ and draw the (incorrect) Hasse diagram of this part of the graph, we would have a connected below only with b . Granted, this will not happen since $a = b$.

Proposition 4.10. *For every $a, b \in E$, $a = b \iff X_a = X_b \cup \{a\}$.*

Proof. If $a = b$ then $X_a = X_b$, since $a \in X_a = X_b$, then $X_b \cup \{a\} = X_b = X_a$. If $X_a = X_b \cup \{a\}$, then axiom 4.8 implies that $a = b$. \square

Definition 4.11. An entity $t \in E$ is called a truly elementary particle (TEP, in short) if and only if $X_t = \{t\}$.

Perhaps we could state that as $X_t = \emptyset \cup \{t\}$, then axiom 4.8 implies that t is equal to whatever entity is represented by \emptyset . Could this be the *real nothingness*? If this is true, then every truly elementary particle would be equal to it, therefore, every entity formed by elementary particles would be a composition of the nothingness with itself.

The idea is engaging; however, there is mistake. If the real nothingness exists as an element of E , denoted as \ominus , then $X_\ominus = \{\ominus\} \neq \emptyset$ and the argument falls. Moreover, even if $X_\ominus = \emptyset$ then axiom 3.4 would imply that $\eta(\{X_\ominus\}) = \emptyset \neq \{\ominus\}$. This contradicts lemma 4.4. On the other hand, if $\ominus \notin E$, which is the idea that we support, then if we define \leq in a larger set that includes both $\{\ominus\}$ and E , then we could have $X_\ominus = \emptyset$. But in this bigger set axiom 4.8 does not necessarily applies. Therefore, we can safely assume that $t \neq \ominus$ and that entities formed by TEPs are not compositions of the nothingness. Furthermore, we can have different truly elementary particles and this does not contradicts axiom 4.8.

Another thing that does not follow from axiom 4.8 is that $(\forall a, b \in E)(X_a \setminus \{a\} = X_b \setminus \{b\} \implies a = b)$. In fact, $X_a \setminus \{a\} = X_b \setminus \{b\}$ implies that $X_a = (X_b \setminus \{b\}) \cup \{a\}$. For axiom 4.8 to apply here, we would require that $(X_b \setminus \{b\}) \cup \{a\} = X_b \cup \{a\}$ which follows if and only if $a = b$. It is the other way around as axiom 4.8 follows from $(\forall a, b \in E)(X_a \setminus \{a\} = X_b \setminus \{b\} \implies a = b)$. That being said, we have no need to accept such a strong statement. Part of the reason is that it implies that every truly elementary particle is equal to each other and this would collapse everything formed by them to a single point.

Proposition 4.12. *Let E_X be the set $\{Y \subset E : (\exists e \in E)(Y = X_e)\}$, there exists a bijection between E and E_X .*

Proof. Let $\phi : E \rightarrow E_X$ be the function defined as $\phi(e) = X_e$. It is a well-defined function since X_e is unique for each $e \in E$ and for every $e \in E$, $\phi(e) \in E_X$. ϕ is injective since $\phi(e_1) = \phi(e_2)$ implies that $X_{e_1} = X_{e_2}$, i.e., $e_1 \leq e_2$ and $e_2 \leq e_1$. It follows that $e_1 = e_2$.

Lastly, it is surjective since $Y \in E_x$ implies that there exists some $e \in E$ such that $Y = X_e$, i.e., $\phi(e) = Y$. \square

From this proposition and its proof, we can deduce that every natural entity is completely determined by its elements.

Corollary 4.13. $(\forall a, b \in E)(a \neq b \iff X_a \neq X_b)$.

Proof. Since $\phi : E \rightarrow E_X$ defined as $\phi(e) = X_e$ is a bijection, it is injective, then $a \neq b \implies \phi(a) \neq \phi(b)$. On the other hand, if $\phi(a) \neq \phi(b)$ then $a \neq b$ because ϕ is a well-defined function. Therefore, $a \neq b \iff \phi(a) \neq \phi(b)$ with $\phi(a) = X_a$ and $\phi(b) = X_b$. \square

5. THE ALGEBRAIC NE-CONNECTION

In this section we will present the $\eta - SNE$ axiomatic system upon which we will be able to define the function that will give rise to the algebra of NE-connections. First, let us define a subspace of E called the subspace of natural structures denoted by SNE . Similar to E , SNE acquires its properties from axioms that involve η . As a subspace of E , its elements are also point-like, therefore at this stage NEs would be taken as primitives that will acquire some of their properties from the axiomatic system that will be presented. These properties will cover part of their canonical representation as (X, D, C) , naturally, they will be some of the properties of X and C .

Let us start by defining a subset E that will be defined and denoted as follows.

$$(4) \quad E_n := \{e \in E : (\exists w \in SNE)(e \leq w)\}$$

In other words, E_n is the collection of natural entities that are part of NEs.

Proposition 5.1. $SNE \subset E_n$.

Proof. For every $n \in SNE$, $n \leq n$, then $n \in E_n$. □

In the following we present a working definition of NE-connected entities.

Definition 5.2. Any collection of natural entities $N \subset E$ is said to be NE-connected if and only if there exists an NE, $n \in SNE$, and a subset $Y \subset E$ such that $N \subset Y$ and $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{n\}$.

Since the aim of this paper is to analyze the algebra of NE-connections, we are bound to consider only pairs of NE-connected elements.

Proposition 5.3. *Any pair of elements of an NE is NE-connected.*

Proof. For any $n \in SNE$, suppose $e_1, e_2 \in X_n$ not necessarily different, then $\{e_1, e_2\} \subset X_n$ while $\eta(\{X_n\}) = \{n\}$ by lemma 4.4. It follows that $\{e_1, e_2\}$ is NE-connected. □

Note that saying that “ $\{e_1, e_2\}$ is NE-connected” is equivalent to say that “ e_1 and e_2 are NE-connected”. The latter will be used more frequently.

With these concepts, we define the following subset of $E_n \times E_n$

$$(5) \quad E_s := \{(a, b) \in E_n \times E_n : \eta(\{\{a, b\}\}) \subset SNE\}$$

Then E_s is a collection of ordered pairs of natural entities that are NE-connected, moreover, it is the collection of *all* the pairs that are NE-connected.

First, let us propose a strong axiom that states that every part of an NE is, in fact, an NE. This property is called *structuralizing effect of NEs*.

Axiom 5.4. $(\forall n \in SNE, \forall Y \subset E)(n \in \eta(\{Y\}) \implies (I \subset Y \implies \eta(\{I\}) \subset SNE))$.

In case $I = \emptyset$, by axiom 3.4, $\eta(\{I\}) = \emptyset$ which is a subset of SNE . Then both axioms are compatible. Axiom 5.4 informally says that every non-empty collection of parts of an NE is projected by η to an NE.

Proposition 5.5. *Let $P \subset E \times E$ be the set of pairs of entities that are NE-connected, then $P = E_s$.*

Proof. For any $(a, b) \in E_s$, $\eta(\{\{a, b\}\}) \subset SNE$. Since $\{a, b\} \neq \emptyset$, let $\eta(\{\{a, b\}\}) = \{n\}$, $n \in SNE$, then a and b are NE-connected, thus $E_s \subset P$. On the other hand, suppose $(c, d) \in P$ then c and d are NE-connected, i.e., there exists $Y \subset E$ and $m \in SNE$ such that $\{c, d\} \subset Y$ and $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{m\}$. This implies that $c \leq m$ and $d \leq m$, therefore $(c, d) \in E_n \times E_n$. Finally, axiom 5.4 implies that $\eta(\{\{c, d\}\}) \subset SNE$, thus $(c, d) \in E_s$. We conclude that $P = E_s$. \square

We can show that NE-connections are symmetric in the following sense.

Proposition 5.6. $(\forall (e_1, e_2) \in E_s)((e_2, e_1) \in E_s)$.

Proof. Note that if $(e_1, e_2) \in E_s$, then $e_1, e_2 \in E_n$ which implies that $(e_2, e_1) \in E_n \times E_n$. Since by hypothesis, $\eta(\{\{e_1, e_2\}\}) \subset SNE$, then $\eta(\{\{e_2, e_1\}\}) \subset SNE$, this implies that $(e_2, e_1) \in E_s$. \square

Axiom 3.3 allows us to we define the following function

$$(6) \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \bullet : & E_s & \rightarrow & SNE \\ & (e_1, e_2) & \mapsto & \bullet(e_1, e_2) \in \eta(\{\{e_1, e_2\}\}) \end{array}$$

To remark the algebraic nature of this function, we denote $\bullet(e_1, e_2)$ by $e_1 \bullet e_2$. We then say that e_1 and e_2 *generate* the NE $e_1 \bullet e_2$. \bullet stands for all interactions that NE-connect a pair of elements and act simultaneously. Needless to say, \bullet accounts for both direct and indirect NE-connections.

It is routine to show that \bullet is a function. First, its domain is a set and so the codomain. For every element (a, b) of the domain E_s , $\eta(\{\{a, b\}\}) \subset SNE$ by definition of E_s . Then we can *choose* one element of this non-empty set as $\bullet(e_1, e_2)$. Finally, the association is unique since $\eta(\{\{a, b\}\})$ is a singleton.

Theorem 5.7. *The function \bullet is surjective.*

Proof. For every $n \in SNE$, $(n, n) \in E_s$. Indeed, we had already showed that $SNE \subset E_n$, then $(n, n) \in E_n \times E_n$. By axiom 3.2, $\eta(\{\{n, n\}\}) = \eta(\{\{n\}\}) = \{n\} \subset SNE$. Therefore there exists an element $(n, n) \in E_s$ such that $\bullet(n, n) \in \{n\}$, i.e., $\bullet(n, n) = n$. \square

Corollary 5.8. *For any $(e, e) \in E_s$, $e \bullet e = e$.*

Proof. Since $\eta(\{\{e\}\}) = \{e\}$, the result follows. This also implies that if $(e, e) \in E_s$, $e \in SNE$. \square

Corollary 5.9. *For any $e \in E_n$, $(e, e) \in E_s \iff e \in SNE$.*

Proof. This follows from corollary 5.8 and the proof of theorem 5.7. \square

This implies that every NE is NE-connected with itself. However, for an arbitrary $e \in E_n$, we cannot say that $e \bullet e = e$ because (e, e) is not necessarily an element of E_s .

It is clear that \bullet is not an internal law of composition in E_n ; however, it is also not an internal law in SNE , because this would imply that every NE is NE-connected with every other NE, which is not supported by evidence. That being said, it could be true if the multiverse is an NE, in this case $E_s = E_n \times E_n$ which has not been required so

far. In the next section we will see that within NEs, a restriction of \bullet works exactly like an internal law of composition. In this sense, every NE is an space in its own right.

Observe that \bullet is (most likely) not injective. Indeed, if we accept that there exists $(a, b) \in E_s$ such that $a \neq b$ which is natural to accept, then $a \bullet b = n$ and $n \bullet n = n$, however $(n, n) \neq (a, b)$.

Now, we will propose the last axiom of the η – *SNE* axiomatic system that partially defines *SNE*.

Axiom 5.10. *For any $Y_1, Y_2 \subset E$ such that $Y_1 \cap Y_2 \neq \emptyset$ and $\eta(\{Y_1\}), \eta(\{Y_2\}) \subset SNE$, it follows that $\eta(\{Y_1 \cup Y_2\}) \subset SNE$. Moreover, if $\eta(\{Y_1\}) = \{m_1\}$ and $\eta(\{Y_2\}) = \{m_2\}$, then $\eta(\{Y_1 \cup Y_2\}) = \{m_1 \bullet m_2\}$.*

In other words, if two collections of entities which share at least one entity are NEs, then both collections form a single NE.

Finally, the transitivity of NE-connections is shown in the following proposition.

Proposition 5.11. $(\forall (e_1, e_2), (e_2, e_3) \in E_s)((e_1, e_3) \in E_s)$.

Proof. Let $Y_1 = \{e_1, e_2\}$ and $Y_2 = \{e_2, e_3\}$, if $(e_1, e_2), (e_2, e_3) \in E_s$, then $\eta(\{Y_1\}) = \{n_1\} \subset SNE$ and $\eta(\{Y_2\}) = \{n_2\} \subset SNE$ while $Y_1 \cap Y_2 \neq \emptyset$. Applying axiom 5.10, $\eta(\{Y_1 \cup Y_2\}) \subset SNE$, i.e., $\eta(\{\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}\}) \subset SNE$. Since $\{e_1, e_3\} \subset \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$, then axiom 5.4 implies that $\eta(\{\{e_1, e_3\}\}) \subset SNE$. Finally, since $(e_1, e_2), (e_2, e_3) \in E_s \subset E_n \times E_n$, then $e_1, e_3 \in E_n$, i.e., $(e_1, e_3) \in E_n \times E_n$. Thus $\eta(\{\{e_1, e_3\}\}) \subset SNE$ guarantees that $(e_1, e_3) \in E_s$. \square

Proposition 5.12. *The function $\bullet : E_s \rightarrow SNE$ is associative in the following sense, $\bullet(a, \bullet(b, c)) = \bullet(\bullet(a, b), c)$, i.e., $a \bullet (b \bullet c) = (a \bullet b) \bullet c$.*

Proof. Suppose $\bullet(a, \bullet(b, c))$ is well-defined. Since $\bullet(b, c) = b \bullet c$, $\eta(\{\{b, c\}\}) = \{b \bullet c\}$. Similarly $\eta(\{\{a, b \bullet c\}\}) = \{a \bullet (b \bullet c)\}$, this is equivalent to say that

$$\eta(\{\{a\} \cup \{b \bullet c\}\}) = \{a \bullet (b \bullet c)\}$$

We can apply axiom 3.9, then $\eta(\{\{a, b, c\}\}) = \{a \bullet (b \bullet c)\}$. Moreover, as $\{a, b\} \subset \{a, b, c\}$, then axiom 5.4 implies that

$$\eta(\{\{a, b\}\}) = \{a \bullet b\} \subset SNE$$

Then, by axiom 3.6, $\eta(\{\{a \bullet b\} \cup \{c\}\}) = \{a \bullet (b \bullet c)\}$. The definition of \bullet implies that $\eta(\{\{c, a \bullet b\}\}) = \{(a \bullet b) \bullet c\}$, therefore $a \bullet (b \bullet c) = (a \bullet b) \bullet c$.

If we suppose that $\bullet(\bullet(a, b), c)$ is well-defined, an analogous procedure guarantees that $a \bullet (b \bullet c) = (a \bullet b) \bullet c$. \square

6. NES AS SPACES IN THEMSELVES

In this section, we will begin with the algebra of NE-connections which is the algebra of \bullet . For this, a crucial step is guarantee that \bullet behaves as an internal law of composition in certain sets. Thus, we start by showing that \bullet is an internal law of composition in every X_n for $n \in SNE$.

Proposition 6.1. *For any $n \in SNE$, X_n meets the following properties.*

- (1) $\eta(\{X_n\}) = \{n\} \subset SNE$,
- (2) $(\forall x \in X_n, \forall e \in E)(e \leq x \implies e \in X_n)$,
- (3) $(\forall \{x_i\}_{i \in I} \subset X_n, \exists y \in X_n, \forall i \in I)(x_i \leq y)$.

Proof. The first property follows directly from lemma 4.4. The second property follows from the transitivity of \leq (theorem 4.3, item 3). For the third property, if $I = \emptyset$ then it is vacuously guaranteed. If $I \neq \emptyset$, since $n \in X_n$, it is enough to take $y = n$. \square

Corollary 6.2. (X_n, \leq) is a directed set, i.e.,

- (1) $(\forall x \in X_n)(x \leq x)$.
- (2) $(\forall x_1, x_2, x_3 \in X_n)(x_1 \leq x_2 \wedge x_2 \leq x_3 \implies x_1 \leq x_3)$.
- (3) $(\forall x_1, x_2 \in X_n, \exists y \in X_n)(x_1 \leq y \wedge x_2 \leq y)$.

Proof. The first and second property follow from the fact that (X_n, \leq) is a poset which follows from the fact that being a poset is a hereditary property. For the third property, let $\{x_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a family of two elements, x_1 and x_2 , then proposition 6.1 item 3 implies that the condition is met. \square

Corollary 6.3. $(\forall n \in SNE)(X_n \subset SNE)$.

Proof. $\forall x \in X_n$, $\{x\} \subset X_n$, since $\eta(\{X_n\}) = \{n\} \subset SNE$, then by axiom 5.4, $\eta(\{\{x\}\}) \subset SNE$. Since $x \in E$, by axiom 3.2, we know that $\eta(\{\{x\}\}) = \{x\}$, therefore $\{x\} \subset SNE$, then $X_n = \cup_{x \in X_n} \{x\} \subset SNE$. \square

This corollary tells us that every element of an NE is an NE. This is the best example of the power of axiom 5.4.

Proposition 6.4. For any $n \in SNE$, if $U \subset E$ satisfies the properties in proposition 6.1, then $U = X_n$.

Proof. Fix $n \in SNE$, then if $U \subset E$ satisfies the properties in proposition 6.1, i.e.,

- (1) $\eta(\{U\}) = \{n\} \subset SNE$,
- (2) $(\forall x \in U, \forall e \in E)(e \leq x \implies e \in X_n)$,
- (3) $(\forall \{x_i\}_{i \in I} \subset U, \exists y \in U, \forall i \in I)(x_i \leq y)$.

The first property implies that $U \neq \emptyset$. For every $u \in U$, $u \leq n$ by definition of \leq , thus $U \subset X_n$. Consider the family $\{u\}_{u \in U} \subset U$, then property 3 implies that there exists $u_M \in U$ such that $\forall u \in U$, $u \leq u_M$, i.e., u_M is the maximum in U , therefore $U \subset X_{u_M}$. Property 2 implies that every $e \in E$ such that $e \leq u_M$ is an element of U , therefore $X_{u_M} \subset U$. We conclude that $U = X_{u_M}$. We know that $\eta(\{X_{u_M}\}) = \{u_M\}$, therefore $\eta(\{U\}) = \{u_M\}$, lastly, property 1 implies that $n = u_M$, then $U = X_n$. \square

Therefore, those three properties of proposition 6.1 characterize X_n .

Lemma 6.5. $(\forall n \in SNE, \forall x_1, x_2 \in X_n)((x_1, x_2) \in E_s)$

Proof. If $x_1, x_2 \in X_n$, then by corollary 6.3, $x_1, x_2 \in SNE$ which is a subset of E_n by proposition 5.1. Then $(x_1, x_2) \in E_n \times E_n$. On the other hand, by axiom 5.4, $\{x_1, x_2\} \subset X_n$ implies that $\eta(\{\{x_1, x_2\}\}) \subset SNE$. It follows from the definition of E_s that $(x_1, x_2) \in E_s$. \square

Corollary 6.6. $(\forall n \in SNE)(X_n \times X_n \subset E_s)$.

Proof. $\forall (x_1, x_2) \in X_n \times X_n, x_1, x_2 \in X_n$, then by lemma 6.5, $(x_1, x_2) \in E_s$. \square

Lemma 6.7. *For every $n \in SNE$, the image of $X_n \times X_n$ by the function \bullet is included in X_n , i.e., $\bullet(X_n \times X_n) \subset X_n$.*

Proof. For every $(x_1, x_2) \in X_n \times X_n, x_1, x_2 \in X_n$, then $x_1, x_2 \leq n$. In other words, there exist $Y_1, Y_2 \subset E$ such that $x_1 \in Y_1, x_2 \in Y_2$ and $\eta(\{Y_1\}) = \{n\} = \eta(\{Y_2\})$. By axiom 3.5, this implies that

$$\eta(\{Y_1 \cup Y_2\}) = \{n\}$$

where $x_1, x_2 \in Y_1 \cup Y_2 = Y$. Now, we know that $\eta(\{\{x_1, x_2\}\}) = \{x_1 \bullet x_2\} = \eta(\{\{x_1 \bullet x_2\}\})$. Then applying axiom 3.5 again, we have that

$$\eta(\{\{x_1, x_2, x_1 \bullet x_2\}\}) = \{x_1 \bullet x_2\}$$

We label $Z = \{x_1, x_2, x_1 \bullet x_2\}$. Now, since $\{x_1, x_2\} \in Z \cap Y$, the intersection is non-empty. Furthermore, $n, x_1 \bullet x_2 \in SNE$. By axiom 5.10, this implies that

$$\eta(\{Y \cup Z\}) = \{n \bullet (x_1 \bullet x_2)\}$$

By proposition 5.12, we know that $n \bullet (x_1 \bullet x_2) = (n \bullet x_1) \bullet x_2$. We will analyze the right-hand side, first, $(n, x_1) \in E_s$ because $x_1, n \in X_n$ and $X_n \times X_n \subset E_s$ (lemma 6.5). Observe that $n \bullet x_1 = n$, indeed

$$\eta(\{Y_1\}) = \eta(\{Y_1 \cup \{x_1\}\}) = \{n\}$$

Using axiom 3.6

$$\eta(\{Y_1 \cup \{x_1\}\}) = \eta(\{\{n\} \cup \{x_1\}\}) = \eta(\{\{x_1, n\}\}) = \{n\}$$

It follows that $n \bullet x_1 = n$. By the same argument, $n \bullet x_2 = n$. Then, $(n \bullet x_1) \bullet x_2 = n$. Finally, since $n \bullet (x_1 \bullet x_2) = (n \bullet x_1) \bullet x_2, \eta(\{Y \cup Z\}) = \{n\}$. Lastly, since $x_1 \bullet x_2 \in Y \cup Z$, then by definition of order, $x_1 \bullet x_2 \leq n$, i.e., $x_1 \bullet x_2 \in X_n$. \square

Theorem 6.8. *For every $n \in SNE$, the restriction of the function \bullet*

$$(7) \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \bullet : & X_n \times X_n & \rightarrow & X_n \\ & (x_1, x_2) & \mapsto & x_1 \bullet x_2 \end{array}$$

is an internal composition law that holds

- (1) $(\forall x_1, x_2 \in X_n)(x_1 \bullet x_2 = x_2 \bullet x_1)$,
- (2) $(\forall x_1, x_2, x_3 \in X_n)(x_1 \bullet (x_2 \bullet x_3) = (x_1 \bullet x_2) \bullet x_3)$.

in other words, (X_n, \bullet) is a commutative semigroup. Furthermore,

3. $(\forall x \in X_n)(x \bullet x = x)$.

Proof. First, since $n \in X_n, X_n \neq \emptyset$. Corollary 6.6 guarantees that $X_n \times X_n \subset E_s$, then we can restrict $\bullet : E_s \rightarrow SNE$ to this non-empty subset. Lemma 6.7 says that the image of $X_n \times X_n$ by \bullet is included in X_n , then we can set the codomain of the restriction $\bullet|_{X_n \times X_n}$ as X_n . This means that \bullet is an internal law of composition in X_n .

Now, $(x_1, x_2) \in X_n \times X_n \subset E_s$ implies that $(x_2, x_1) \in X_n \times X_n$, therefore $\eta(\{\{x_1, x_2\}\}) = \{x_1 \bullet x_2\}$ and $\eta(\{\{x_2, x_1\}\}) = \{x_2 \bullet x_1\}$. Since $\{x_1, x_2\} = \{x_2, x_1\}$, it follows that

$x_1 \bullet x_2 = x_2 \bullet x_1$. For the second property, proposition 5.12 says that \bullet is associative in E_s , then it is associative in every restriction given that the intermediate products are in the domain, since \bullet is an internal law of composition in X_n this condition is met, therefore $x_1 \bullet (x_2 \bullet x_3) = (x_1 \bullet x_2) \bullet x_3$. The last property follows trivially from corollary 5.8 since $(x, x) \in X_n \times X_n \subset E_s$. \square

This is the most important theorem of this section because it gives algebraic structure to X_n . The second property shows the associativity of NE-connections which should not be interpreted as successive steps in the formation of an NE, but as two groups of simultaneous interactions which are also simultaneous. It also enables us to write $x_1 \bullet (x_2 \bullet x_3)$ as $x_1 \bullet x_2 \bullet x_3$ since the order of operation of \bullet is unimportant. Moreover, since \bullet is commutative in X_n ,

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 \bullet (x_2 \bullet x_3) &= x_1 \bullet x_2 \bullet x_3 = x_1 \bullet x_3 \bullet x_2 \\ &= x_2 \bullet x_1 \bullet x_3 = x_2 \bullet x_3 \bullet x_1 \\ &= x_3 \bullet x_1 \bullet x_2 = x_3 \bullet x_2 \bullet x_1 \end{aligned}$$

If we consider the brackets, we would have 12 meaningful products that are equal. The generalized associative and commutative laws of commutative semigroups [5, p. 28] allows us to write “the product” of any collection $\{x_1, \dots, x_m\} \subset X_n$ as $x_1 \bullet \dots \bullet x_m$. This motivates us to propose the following definition with the usual algebraic notation of product.

Definition 6.9. Let $S \subset X_n$ be a non-empty and finite subset $S = \{s_1, \dots, s_m\}$. The (finite) product of the elements of S is defined and denoted as

$$\prod_{s \in S} s := s_1 \bullet s_2 \bullet \dots \bullet s_m$$

Equivalently, we can also write $\prod_{i=1}^m s_i$ when it is necessary to keep track of the number of elements and the particular indexing of S .

If $m = 1$, $\prod_{i=1}^m s_i = s_1$. Keep in mind that whenever we write $\prod_{x \in I} x$ it is implicit that I is finite. To be totally formal we could use a construction of $\prod_{s \in S} s$ such as the one in [4, p. 30]. We take for granted that we use this formalism.

Proposition 6.10. For all $S \subset X_n$, S finite and non-empty, $\prod_{s \in S} s \in X_n$.

Proof. We can write $S = \{s_1, \dots, s_m\}$. We will prove by induction on m that $\prod_{s \in S} s$ is well defined and $\prod_{s \in S} s \in X_n$. If $m = 1$, then $\prod_{s \in S} s = s_1$ which is well defined and an element of X_n . Suppose it holds for m elements and S has $m + 1$ elements, then $\prod_{s \in S \setminus \{s_{m+1}\}} s$ is well defined and an element of X_n . Theorem 6.8 says that \bullet is an internal law of composition of X_n , then as $\prod_{s \in S \setminus \{s_{m+1}\}} s, s_{m+1} \in X_n$, its composition is well defined and $\prod_{s \in S \setminus \{s_{m+1}\}} s \bullet s_{m+1} \in X_n$, in other words, $\prod_{s \in S} s \in X_n$. \square

Definition 6.11. A subset $V \subset E$ is called a NE-subspace if and only if $V \times V \subset E_s$ and $\forall S \subset V$ non-empty and finite, $\prod_{s \in S} s \in V$.

Proposition 6.12. For any $n \in SNE$, X_n is an NE-subspace.

Proof. The proposition follows from theorem 6.8 together with proposition 6.10. \square

Given that for any $w \in X_n$, X_w is also a NE-subspace and $X_w \subset X_n$, then we can say that X_w is a subspace of X_n .

Theorem 6.13. *For every $I \subset X_n$ non-empty and finite, $n \in SNE$, $\eta(\{I\}) = \{\prod_{x \in I} x\}$.*

Proof. Let us start with the trivial cases. If I is a singleton $I = \{x_1\}$, then $\prod_{x \in I} x = x_1$. It follows by axiom 3.2 that $\eta(\{I\}) = \{x_1\}$, i.e., $\eta(\{I\}) = \{\prod_{x \in I} x\}$. If I has two elements x_1 and x_2 , then by definition of the \bullet operator, $\eta(\{x_1, x_2\}) = \{x_1 \bullet x_2\}$, in other words, $\eta(\{I\}) = \{\prod_{x \in I} x\}$.

Now, let $I = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ with $n > 2$. We will prove with an inductive argument that for every $n > 2$, $\eta(\{I\}) = \{\prod_{x \in I} x\}$.

Suppose that $n = 3$, i.e., $I = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$. We divide I into the overlapping sets $L_1 = \{x_1, x_2\}$ and $L_2 = \{x_2, x_3\}$. Since $L_1, L_2 \subset X_n$, then by definition of \bullet , $\eta(\{L_1\}) = \{x_1 \bullet x_2\}$ and $\eta(\{L_2\}) = \{x_2 \bullet x_3\}$. Since $L_1 \cap L_2 \neq \emptyset$ and $\eta(\{L_1\}), \eta(\{L_2\}) \subset SNE$, then by axiom 5.10,

$$\eta(\{L_1 \cup L_2\}) = \{(x_1 \bullet x_2) \bullet (x_2 \bullet x_3)\}$$

By the algebraic properties of \bullet , we have that $(x_1 \bullet x_2) \bullet (x_2 \bullet x_3) = x_1 \bullet x_2 \bullet x_3$. Since $L_1 \cup L_2 = I$, then

$$\eta(\{I\}) = \{x_1 \bullet x_2 \bullet x_3\} = \left\{ \prod_{x \in I} x \right\}$$

Now, suppose that the proposition holds for n and I has $n + 1$ elements. We section I into $I_1 = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and $L_n = \{x_n, x_{n+1}\}$. By the inductive hypothesis, $\eta(\{I_1\}) = \{\prod_{x \in I_1} x\}$. Since $I_1 \cap L_n \neq \emptyset$ and $\eta(\{I_1\}), \eta(\{L_n\}) \subset SNE$, then applying axiom 5.10,

$$\eta(\{I_1 \cup L_n\}) = \{(\prod_{x \in I_1} x) \bullet (x_n \bullet x_{n+1})\}$$

In other words, $\eta(\{I\}) = \{(x_1 \bullet \dots \bullet x_n) \bullet (x_n \bullet x_{n+1})\}$, i.e.,

$$\eta(\{I\}) = \{x_1 \bullet \dots \bullet x_{n+1}\} = \left\{ \prod_{x \in I} x \right\}$$

\square

Can X_n be a group? We know from [4, p. 47] that (X_n, \bullet) is a group if and only if for any $a, b \in X_n$ there are $c, d \in X_n$ such that $a \bullet c = b$ and $d \bullet a = b$. However, this does not hold in general as we see in the following.

Proposition 6.14. *For $n \in SNE$, X_n is a group if and only if n is a TEP.*

Proof. Let $a, b \in X_n$, $a \neq n$, and $b \notin X_a$. Observe that if there is no $b \in X_n$ as above, then $a = n$ by axiom 3.6. If X_n were a group, then there exists $c \in X_n$ such that $a = b \bullet c$, i.e., $b \in X_a$ because $a = \eta(\{\{b \bullet c\}\}) = \eta(\{\{b, c\}\})$ implies $b \leq a$.

Finally, if n is a TEP it is trivial that it is a group. \square

Now, we present a couple of results about the formation of NEs.

Proposition 6.15. *Let $b \in E$ and $n \in SNE$, for every $x \in X_n$,*

$$(b, x) \in E_s \implies (b, n) \in E_s$$

Proof. Since $x \in X_n$ and $n \in X_n$, then $(x, n) \in E_s$ because $X_n \times X_n \subset E_s$ by corollary 6.6. If $(b, x) \in E_s$, then by proposition 5.11 it follows that $(b, n) \in E_s$. \square

The proposition is stated for every $b \in E$, however, $(b, x) \in E_s$ implies that $b \in SNE$ because $\eta(\{\{b, x\}\}) \subset SNE$ implies by axiom 5.4 that $\eta(\{\{b\}\}) \subset SNE$, i.e., $b \in SNE$ (axiom 3.2).

Corollary 6.16. *Let $b \in E$ and $n \in SNE$, for every $x, y \in X_n$,*

$$(b, x) \in E_s \implies (b, y) \in E_s$$

Proof. If $(b, x) \in E_s$, then $(b, n) \in E_s$ by proposition 6.15. Since $y \in X_n$, then $(n, y) \in E_s$. By transitivity $(b, y) \in E_s$. \square

These two results shed light on the behavior of NE-connections. If an entity b is NE-connected to a part of an NE n , then it is NE-connected to n (proposition 6.15) and then it is also NE-connected with every other part of n (corollary 6.16).

Proposition 6.17. *If a non-empty collection of elements $N \subset E$ is NE-connected, then for every non-empty finite subset $I \subset N$, $\prod_{x \in I} x$ is well-defined.*

Proof. If N is NE-connected, then definition 5.2 implies that there exists $n \in SNE$ and a subset $Y \subset E$ such that $N \subset Y$ and $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{n\}$. Let $I \subset N$ be non-empty and finite, then $I \subset X_n$, the proof of proposition 6.10 completes the proof. \square

7. ORDER IN FINITE NES

The commutative semigroup (X_n, \bullet) has some intuitive properties whenever X_n is finite. Recall definition 4.1 and equation (6) where we introduced \leq and \bullet respectively. Both concepts were defined from η , this is conducive to their codefinition (theorem 7.3) and compatibility (theorem 7.4). These properties account for the close connection between the poset (X_n, \leq) and the commutative semigroup (X_n, \bullet) .

Definition 7.1. A finite NE is any $n \in SNE$ such that X_n is finite.

We know that (E, \leq) is a partially ordered space, then as X_n is a non-empty subset of E , (X_n, \leq) is a partially ordered set.

Lemma 7.2. *For every finite $n \in SNE$, $x_i, x_j \in X_n$ implies that*

$$(8) \quad x_i \leq x_j \iff (\exists x \in X_n)(x \bullet x_i = x_j)$$

Proof. We will show the equivalence by proving both implications. First, suppose $x_i \leq x_j$, then

$$(\exists Y \subset X_n)(\eta(\{Y\}) = \{x_j\} \wedge x_i \in Y)$$

Since X_n is finite, Y is finite. Since $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{x_j\} \neq \emptyset$, then the contrapositive of axiom 3.4 implies that $Y \neq \emptyset$. Since Y is finite and non-empty, then by theorem 6.13,

$$\prod_{y \in Y} y = x_j$$

Let $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_m\}$, then we can write

$$\prod_{i=1}^m y_i = x_j$$

Now, since $x_i \in Y$, then we can reindex Y so that $y_n = x_i$, then

$$\left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-1} y_i \right) \bullet x_i = x_j$$

Since \bullet is an internal law of composition in X_n , then every finite product of elements of X_n is an element of X_n . Then $\prod_{i=1}^{n-1} y_i \in X_n$, call this product as x . We have proved that $(\exists x \in X)(x \bullet x_i = x_j)$.

For the other implication, suppose there is a pair $x_i, x_j \in X_n$ such that

$$(\exists x \in X_n)(x \bullet x_i = x_j)$$

Then define $Y := \{x, x_i\} \subset X_n$, since $(x, x_i) \in E_s$ because $X_n \times X_n \subset E_s$, then by definition of \bullet , $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{x \bullet x_i\} = \{x_j\}$. This shows that

$$(\exists Y \subset X_n)(\eta(\{Y\}) = x_j \wedge x_i \in Y)$$

which implies by definition that $x_i \leq x_j$. □

With this equivalence, the following theorem become apparent.

Theorem 7.3. *For every finite $n \in SNE$,*

$$(\forall x_i, x_j \in X_n)(x_i \leq x_j \iff x_i \bullet x_j = x_j)$$

Proof. If $x_i \leq x_j$, then since X_n is finite, lemma 7.2 implies that $\exists x \in X_n$ such that $x \bullet x_i = x_j$, then we “multiply” x_i in both sides and apply associativity of \bullet

$$x \bullet (x_i \bullet x_i) = x_j \bullet x_i$$

Since $x_i \bullet x_i = x_i$ and \bullet is commutative, we write $x \bullet x_i = x_i \bullet x_j$. Since $x \bullet x_i = x_j$, we conclude that $x_i \bullet x_j = x_j$.

For the second implication, suppose $x_i \bullet x_j = x_j$, then setting $x = x_j$, $\exists x \in X$ such that $x \bullet x_i = x_j$, therefore $x_i \leq x_j$. □

Theorem 7.4. *In every finite X_n , collection of elements of a finite NE , \leq is compatible with \bullet in the sense that*

$$(\forall a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 \in X_n)(a_1 \leq b_1 \wedge a_2 \leq b_2 \implies a_1 \bullet a_2 \leq b_1 \bullet b_2)$$

Proof. By theorem 7.3, $a_1 \leq b_1$ and $a_2 \leq b_2$ imply that $a_1 \bullet b_1 = b_1$ and $a_2 \bullet b_2 = b_2$. Let $x = b_1 \bullet b_2$, clearly $x \in X_n$. Then $x \bullet (a_1 \bullet a_2) = (b_1 \bullet b_2) \bullet (a_1 \bullet a_2)$ applying associativity and commutativity we have that $x \bullet (a_1 \bullet a_2) = (b_1 \bullet a_1) \bullet (b_2 \bullet a_2)$, this in turn implies that $x \bullet (a_1 \bullet a_2) = b_1 \bullet b_2$. Since $x, a_1 \bullet a_2, b_1 \bullet b_2 \in X_n$, by lemma 7.2, this is equivalent to say that $a_1 \bullet a_2 \leq b_1 \bullet b_2$. \square

Corollary 7.5. *Every finite X_n is an ordered semigroup.*

Proof. This follows from theorem 7.4 and the definition of ordered semigroups. \square

Corollary 7.6. *For every pair $(a, b) \in E_s$, $a \bullet b$ is the smallest NE among the finite NEs that has a and b as parts of it, in other words, let SNE_f be the subspace of finite NEs,*

$$(\forall (a, b) \in E_s, \forall n \in SNE_f)(a \leq n \wedge b \leq n \implies a \bullet b \leq n)$$

Proof. If $a \leq n \wedge b \leq n$, then $a, b \in X_n$ with X_n finite. It follows that $a \bullet b \leq n \bullet n$, i.e., $a \bullet b \leq n$. \square

Of course it could be that for some $(a, b) \in E_s$ there is no $n \in SNE_f$ such that $a \leq n \wedge b \leq n$. This may happen if either X_a or X_b are not finite sets. However, even in these cases, corollary 7.6 is tautologically true since everything follows from a false statement.

We could recap the order of definitions as follows

$$\eta \xrightarrow{\text{def.4.1}} \leq \xrightarrow{\text{eq.(4)}} E_n \xrightarrow{\text{eq.(5)}} E_s \xrightarrow{\text{eq.(6)}} \bullet$$

and now

$$\bullet \xrightarrow{\text{thm.7.3}} \leq$$

It may appear that this is circular reasoning and that we are defining \leq from \leq . This is not true since to define E_s we require E_n and η , and to define \bullet we require E_s and η . The most we could say is that we can define \leq from \leq and η but even this is not true because there is no transitivity in definitions.

8. THE CONNECTION BETWEEN C_n AND X_n

We have analyzed in depth the mathematics of X_n of the canonical representation of n as (X_n, D_n, C_n) . We have also linked X_n and C_n implicitly when we stated that every non-empty subcollection of X_n is NE-connected. Since C_n is the family of collections of NE-connections among the elements of X_n , this implies that for every non-empty subcollection of X_n there exists a collection *in* C_n with at least one element which represents the NE-connection between the elements of the given subcollection of X_n . In this section we will briefly explore the mathematics of C_n in order to explain and formalize this claim and the link between C_n and X_n .

Let $\wp^*(X_n)$ be the set of non-empty subsets of X_n . We can define C_n as follows

$$C_n := \{ \{ \omega_i \}_{i \in N_\ell} \}_{\ell \in \wp^*(X_n)}$$

such that $(\forall \ell \in \wp^*(X_n))(N_\ell \neq \emptyset)$. This definition requires some explanation. First, $\{N_\ell\}_{\ell \in \wp^*(X_n)}$ is a family whose elements are the index sets of the families $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_\ell}$ of

NE-connections. The condition $N_\ell \neq \emptyset$ is an axiomatic definition of C_n . Currently, it is admissible that for $\ell, \ell' \in \wp^*(X_n)$ with $\ell \neq \ell'$, $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_\ell} = \{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_{\ell'}}$. We cannot disregard this possibility unless after the theory of NE-connections is developed, some result shows that this is impossible. Observe that $N_\ell = N_{\ell'}$ does not imply neither that $\ell = \ell'$ nor $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_\ell} = \{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_{\ell'}}$.

It has been stated that $\prod_{x \in I} x$ represents the existence of at least one NE-connection that “connects” the elements of I . By definition of product, I is finite and non-empty, thus $I \in \wp^*(X_n)$. This implies that there exists a non-empty set N_I such that $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_I} \in C_n$ and every ω_i represents an NE-connection between the elements of I . If N_I has one element, then I is NE-connected *by 1 NE-connection*. For instance, if n is a TEP, then $I = \{n\}$ could have an associated a family $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_I}$ with only one element, ω_1 . It is also likely for a TEP t in some X_n with at least 2 elements, that while t NE-connects with another element $a \in X_n$ it also NE-connects with itself through this interaction, therefore its associated family $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_{\{t\}}}$ could have more than one element. In general, indirect NE-connections are expected to generate more elements in $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_{\{t\}}}$.

It is also possible that for a given subcollection of elements $I \subset X_n$ some NE-connections that NE-connected this subcollection of elements are in two different elements of C_n , i.e., that there is at least another family $\{\delta_j\}_{j \in N_I}$ besides $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_I}$ in C_n such that some δ_j is an NE-connection that NE-connects I . Without a theory of NE-connections, we are treading on obscure waters and can only make educated guesses.

Another notation that should be taken into account is the brackets notation of [1]. In the brackets notation, the NE-connections of a non-empty subcollection $I \subset X_n$ is represented by $[I]$. Therefore, any ω_i in $\{\omega_i\}_{i \in N_I}$ could be represented as $[I]$. This is useful when the identity of the exact NE-connection is not required for the analysis or to simplify notation.

For instance, wholeness is a property of NEs where every pair of elements are NE-connected [2]. This could be succinctly expressed as

$$(\forall a, b \in X_n, \exists p \in C_n)([a, b] \in p)$$

This property is directly related with the closure of X_n . We could also assert that

$$(9) \quad (\forall \{a, b\} \subset E, \forall p \in C_n)([\{a, b\}] \in p \implies a, b \in X_n)$$

This is the co-definition of C_n and X_n . Another property is the expansion of C_n which is formulated as

$$(\forall p, p' \in C_n)([\{a, b\}] \in p \wedge [\{b, c\}] \in p' \implies (\exists p^* \in C_n)([\{a, b, c\}] \in p^*))$$

This property follows naturally from the transitivity of NE-connections.

Why should we be interested in studying C_n if apparently every element of C_n can be derived from subsets of X_n ? Well, because this is only apparent, in reality, the same pair elements x_1, x_2 of X_n can be NE-connected through different NE-connections with different characteristics as it was mentioned earlier. Knowing that $x_1, x_2 \in X_n$ only tell us that there exists at least one NE-connection between them. It does not tells us

neither how many NE-connections are between them nor what type of NE-connections are. That being said, it is likely that most of those properties can be derived from X_n with the exception of NE-connections that are not formed by elements of X_n neither directly nor indirectly. The classic example of a gas trapped in a naturally formed cave is spot-on. Here, there is no other NE-connection between the gas molecules besides the fact that they are trapped inside the same cave which is not part of the gas. The cave NE-connects them without being part of the NE.

9. FINAL REMARKS

The independence and consistency of all the axioms proposed here should be analyzed later on. However, even after proving independence and consistency, it is likely that all of these axioms can be derived from a more fundamental and different set of axioms that explains NEs. In other words, an axiomatic system that does not take NEs as primitives. In this way, this work and that future result would be complementary.

In section 4, we explained why we can consider truly elementary particles $t \in E$ and the real nothingness \ominus as different entities. However, it remains to study the relationship between \ominus and t provided by $X_t = \emptyset \cup \{t\} = X_\ominus \cup \{t\}$.

Given that we have equipped X_n with the algebraic structure of a commutative semigroup (X_n, \bullet) , all of the tools and constructions that are defined for semigroups such as Noetherian semigroups, quotients of semigroups, etc. can be readily applied on X_n . The implications of each of this techniques on the theory of natural structures should be studied as an independent research.

We discussed in section 6 that only in the case $X_n = \{n\}$ we can take this semigroup as a group. That does not prevent that (X_n, \bullet) could be extended into a monoid by adding the element \ominus . For this, \bullet should be accordingly redefined to accommodate compositions with \ominus which would trivially result into the same element, i.e., $x \bullet \ominus = x$.

We need to remark that given that every element of (X_n, \bullet) is idempotent, we cannot possibly extend X_n to a bigger set $\mathbb{X}_n = X_n \cup Z_n$ such that (\mathbb{X}_n, \bullet) is a group unless $X_n = \{n\}$. This complements the idea portrayed in proposition 6.14. Indeed, let e be the identity of the group \mathbb{X}_n and x any element of X_n . Given that $x \bullet x = x$, then $x \bullet x \bullet x^{-1} = x \bullet x^{-1} = e$, i.e., $x \bullet e = e$ then $x = e$. Thus $X_n \subset \{e\}$ and X_n is non-empty, therefore $X_n = \{e\} = \{n\}$. Moreover, since (X_n, \bullet) is a commutative semigroup, the embedding of (X_n, \bullet) in a group would be possible if and only if it is cancellative [3, p. 34], i.e., if $x \bullet y = x \bullet z$ implies that $y = z$ for any $x, y, z \in X_n$. However, we observe that if X_n has at least two elements, then it is not cancellative. Indeed, suppose $x_i, x_j \in X_n$ are two different elements, then $x_i \bullet x_j \in X_n$. Now $(x_i \bullet x_j) \bullet x_i = x_i \bullet x_j$ and $(x_i \bullet x_j) \bullet x_j = x_i \bullet x_j$. However it does not follow from $(x_i \bullet x_j) \bullet x_i = (x_i \bullet x_j) \bullet x_j$ that $x_i = x_j$. In summary, the semigroup (X_n, \bullet) is a group if and only if n is a TEP and in general cannot be extended to a group nor embedded into a group.

Another open question is whether there could be NE-subspaces that are not the collection of elements of some NE.

Lastly, we provide some comments regarding C_n and D_n . In terms of information, as sets, C_n is richer than X_n . From equation (9), we can take the pair $\{a, a\}$, therefore,

if there exists some $p \in C_n$ such that $[\{a, a\}] \in p$, it follows that $a \in X_n$ and we know that for every $a \in X_n$ there exists such $p \in C_n$. Therefore, everything about X_n , as a set, can be recovered from C_n . However, it is possible that the structure of X_n as a poset or as a commutative semigroup cannot be inferred from C_n . Therefore, C_n and X_n partially describe each other but there are inherent properties of each of them that cannot be inferred from the other.

Regarding the distribution of NEs, in [1] a step forward was taken with the development of its representation. We can comment that the distribution of every element is deeply related with the types NE-connections in which it takes part. Trivially, every element of an NE is NE-connected with every other element; however, the difference between types of NE-connections shapes the distribution of the element. That being said, the strength of NE-connection does not necessarily imply spatial nearness. Two elements can be more strongly NE-connected than another pair while being more spatially separated. This counterintuitive pattern is exemplified by the nuclear force. The nuclear force is repulsive at short distances and attractive at larger distances [6, p. 231].

In summary, D_n , the distribution of n , is partially explained by X_n and C_n . However, there is an inherent component of D_n that cannot be recovered from C_n or X_n just like how C_n and X_n are related.

10. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. F. Peña-Garcia express his gratitude towards Marco Peña-Garcia for his helpful comments both in the philosophical aspects of this research and the redaction of the manuscript. A special thanks to W. Cabrera-Febola for his insightful comments at the very beginning of the investigation.

REFERENCES

1. Walter Cabrera-Febola, *A brief introduction to the mathematics of natural structures (unpublished results)*.
2. ———, *ON NATURAL STRUCTURES: The unification of nature*, Spacetime and Substance **5** (2004), no. 1, 34–41.
3. A. H. Clifford and G. B. Preston, *The algebraic theory of semigroups*, vol. 1, American Mathematical Society, 1977.
4. Leon Warren Cohen and Gertrude Ehrlich, *The structure of the real number system*, The University Series in Undergraduate Mathematics, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1963.
5. Thomas W Hungerford, *Algebra*, vol. 73, Springer-Verlag New York, Inc., 1974.
6. Bogdan Povh, Klaus Rith, Christoph Scholz, and Frank Zetsche, *Particles and nuclei: An introduction to the physical concepts*, fifth edition ed., Springer, 2006.

ENSEMBLE FOR THE FUNDAMENTAL STUDY OF NATURE AND MATHEMATICS, LIMA, PERÚ.
DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL MAYOR DE SAN MARCOS, LIMA, PERÚ.
Email address: francescoapg@gmail.com

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL MAYOR DE SAN MARCOS, LIMA, PERÚ.
Email address: medinadiazmeyor@gmail.com

A. AXIOMATIC SYSTEMS

 $\eta - E$ axiomatic system

Axiom 1. Let $V^E := \{\{\{e\}\} : e \in E\}$, for every $\{\{e\}\} \in V^E$, $\eta(\{\{e\}\}) = \{e\}$.

Axiom 2. For every $Y \subset E$ non-empty, there exists a unique entity $\hat{e} \in E$ such that $\eta(\{Y\}) = \{\hat{e}\}$.

Axiom 3. $\eta(\{\emptyset\}) = \emptyset$.

Axiom 4. For every non-empty family $\{Y_i\}_{i \in I}$ of non-empty subsets of E , such that $(\forall i, j \in I)(\eta(\{Y_i\}) = \eta(\{Y_j\}))$. It follows that for every $j \in I$, $\eta(\{\bigcup_{i \in I} Y_i\}) = \eta(\{Y_j\})$.

Axiom 5. $(\forall I \subset E, \forall J \subset I)(\eta(\{I\}) = \{n\} \wedge \eta(\{J\}) = \{m\} \implies \eta(\{\{m\} \cup I \setminus J\}) = \{n\})$

Axiom 6. $(\forall I, J \subset E)(\eta(\{J\}) = \{m\} \wedge \eta(\{I \cup \{m\}\}) = \{n\} \implies \eta(\{I \cup J\}) = \{n\})$

Axiom 7. For every $a, b \in E$, if $X_a = X_b \cup \{a\}$, then $a = b$.

 $\eta - SNE$ axiomatic system

Axiom 8. $(\forall n \in SNE, \forall Y \subset E)(n \in \eta(\{Y\}) \implies (I \subset Y \implies \eta(\{I\}) \subset SNE))$.

Axiom 9. For any $Y_1, Y_2 \subset E$ such that $Y_1 \cap Y_2 \neq \emptyset$ and $\eta(\{Y_1\}), \eta(\{Y_2\}) \subset SNE$, it follows that $\eta(\{Y_1 \cup Y_2\}) \subset SNE$. Moreover, if $\eta(\{Y_1\}) = \{m_1\}$ and $\eta(\{Y_2\}) = \{m_2\}$, then $\eta(\{Y_1 \cup Y_2\}) = \{m_1 \bullet m_2\}$.